

Communication Plan HOLOSEU

Deliverable 7.2 Update M14

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1 Summary

Communication is essential within HOLOSEU, as it serves as the main method for ensuring the transfer of knowledge and the adoption of results during and after the project's duration. The strategic objectives, target audiences, key messages, and narratives of the project act as a reference for the project's actions in relevant areas. All communication activities of HOLOSEU will be grounded in this communication plan, which includes a detailed outline of communication messages, target groups, communication tools, channels, and strategies for effectively disseminating project results. The communication plan also establishes tailored key performance indicators (KPIs) for the project's outreach efforts, aimed at quantitatively assessing the effectiveness of communication activities. A timeline for implementation and updates is included.

The first version of this deliverable was handed in on the 28th of March 2025. The current version is an update in month 14, and the document will be reviewed and updated in Months 25 and 36 of the project. HOLOSEU has a well-crafted graphic identity. Traditional marketing methods, such as project logos, websites, leaflets, posters, and templates, will be integrated with other communication tools, such as social media posts and blog articles.

2 Introduction

HOLOSEU acknowledges the significance of clear and targeted strategies for communication of research results, starting as early as possible in the project's timeline. The deliverable outlines the translation of research results into formats that can be understood and presented to various audiences, including the media and the public. Communication is crucial for maximizing the value of the research outputs generated within the project. By leveraging HOLOSEU's stakeholder mapping exercise and identifying the most effective communication tools in terms of sustainability and outreach potential.

3 Objectives

The main objectives of the Communications Plan are to ensure timely project milestone communication, maximize research impact through publications and presentations, and enhance HOLOSEU's visibility in European agriculture via stakeholder engagement and partnerships. The guidelines emphasize that all messages will be tailored to specific audiences, distributed through appropriate channels, and based on the information needs of the recipients.

3.1 Communications Objectives

These are our main objectives that are to be achieved by the execution of this Communications Plan.

- Ensure timely project milestone communication.
- Maximize research impact by publishing in reputable journals, presenting at conferences, and engaging diverse audiences.
- Enhance HOLOSEU's visibility and potential in European agriculture via stakeholder engagement, a comprehensive communication strategy, and fostering partnerships.

3.2 Communications Guidelines

To help us meet your objectives, we list all the *guidelines* that are applicable to the dissemination of communications messages within our consortium:

- All messages will be audience-specific
- Messages will be distributed through an appropriate channel
- Communication will be tailored, based on what people need to know
- Official press releases will be coordinated within the consortium
- The project team will update the activities feeding into the communication plan on a regular basis in order to create synergies in the consortium

4 Stakeholders

The section outlines the target audience for HOLOSEU's communication efforts, which includes various stakeholders such as farmers, experts, policymakers, and global scientific communities, while emphasizing the importance of stakeholder analysis to effectively reach these groups and guide dissemination activities. It highlights the necessity of engaging stakeholders to understand their information needs and gather feedback, which will inform project implementation and facilitate knowledge exchange among partners and the broader community.

4.1 Target Audience

In the following we will list and describe each of the audience groups (i.e. stakeholders) that HOLOSEU partners will communicate with.

The project may have the following target audiences:

- Farmers
- Landowners
- Business sector including finance
- Spatial planners
- Experts
- Academia incl. universities, Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR)
- Global scientific communities, like IPCC and UNFCCC
- Policymakers
- Tech professionals
- Industry partners
- Agricultural associations
- Government agencies
- Pilot users

The inclusion of farmers in research initiatives is crucial, as they are the primary stakeholders directly affected by agricultural policies and innovations. Their firsthand experience and knowledge can provide invaluable insights into practical challenges and opportunities within the sector. However, engaging farmers in research formats can be challenging due to factors such as time constraints, or differing priorities among others. Many farmers may find research activities inaccessible or irrelevant to their day-to-day operations. Therefore, it is essential to develop

inclusive and adaptable engagement strategies that resonate with farmers, ensuring their voices are heard and their contributions valued in the research process.

We can offer farmers access to tailored resources and tools that enhance their productivity and sustainability, making research directly applicable to their practices. Additionally, by involving them in collaborative projects and feedback mechanisms, we can ensure that their needs and concerns are addressed, fostering a sense of ownership and partnership in the research outcomes.

In the context of living labs, additional stakeholders that could be involved include:

- Local communities and residents
- NGOs and non-profit organizations focused on agriculture and rural development
- Agricultural extension services
- Technology developers and startups
- Environmental organizations
- Supply chain partners (e.g., distributors and retailers)
- Consumer groups interested in sustainable practices
- International development agencies
- Research institutions
- Media and communication specialists

These stakeholders can contribute diverse perspectives and resources, enriching the living lab environment and enhancing collaborative efforts.

4.2 Stakeholder Identification, Analysis, and Mapping

The communication and dissemination plan is built on a stakeholder analysis to ensure the project’s objectives and results effectively reach all target audiences. This analysis identifies how HOLOSEU will impact or be impacted by different stakeholders, guiding dissemination efforts and advocacy actions. It helps assess the effectiveness of sharing findings and determines any additional steps needed to engage specific stakeholders. The HOLOSEU platform will benefit farmers, advisors, citizens, and researchers dealing with policies such as the Common Agricultural Policy, Climate Action, Green Deals, and SDGs. Stakeholders including policymakers and global scientific communities like the IPCC and UNFCCC will also be involved. A preliminary stakeholder analysis is conducted by partners via an Excel document provided by Fraunhofer ISI (P9). The document included instructions and a template for the partners to add their stakeholders. The partners filled out columns related to stakeholders’ type, their fit in HOLOSEU, PESTEL category, legal form, activity level, and contact details. Table 4.1 summarizes the partners contribution in this section.

Table 4.1: Partners Input for Stakeholder Mapping in Year One.

Partner	Date
Avoin (P2)	May 2 nd 2025
IAPAS (P4)	December 17 th 2025
USAMV (P7)	July 29 th 2025
UNIA (P8)	October 22 nd 2025

4.3 Stakeholders Engagement and Requirement Gathering

Engaging stakeholders and understanding their needs is essential for successful communication. Regular stakeholder engagement will guide work package activities, ensuring HOLOSEU's practical implementation. Partners will use their networks to promote results and facilitate knowledge exchange and gather feedback from farmers, industry associations, academics, government agencies, NGOs, and professional societies. Pilot users and stakeholders will provide feedback for design improvements, and the results will flow directly within WP3.

4.4 Key Messages

The goal is to transform HOLOSIE V3.0 into a tailored HOLOSEU model, which was renamed to Model for Decision-Making in Agri-Environmental Systems (MODASYS), for European agricultural systems, enabling effective planning of sustainable farming practices. This model will also support accurate carbon and environmental footprint assessments to drive climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as facilitate reporting at national, regional, and EU levels.

5 Channels

The core *communications channels* are identified in the following.

5.1 External Communication

External communication is the transmission of the HOLOSEU project to stakeholders outside the project consortium. For optimal outreach to external stakeholders, communication tools will be developed. External communication tools and channels include the HOLOSEU website, peer-reviewed journal publications and conference contributions, newsletters, blogs, social media posts, etc. UCD and partners will provide multilingual information to stakeholders through workshops, articles, and a dedicated web page, ensuring easy understanding.

Farmer data will be collected anonymously under FAIR agreements for model development, with open models and findings accessible via secure repositories like Zenodo.

HOLOSEU plans to utilize the institutional networks and connections of its consortium members to share project activities and outcomes. This will include disseminating information through relevant networks, and platforms, as well as engaging with social media and participating in international events and conferences in collaboration with other research initiatives. The project's primary goal is to establish two-way

communication with stakeholders, enabling the sharing of new results and insights while also collecting knowledge, expertise, and feedback from them.

5.2 Internal Communication

Internal communication is crucial for ensuring team alignment. Key communication tools and channels include regular meetings and quarterly web-based sessions to review progress, methodologies, preliminary results, and draft reports and papers. Additionally, internal communication involves collecting information from partners about their internal and external events (using an Excel template) to ensure communication activities are accurately aligned with their priorities. Internal communications in year one included virtual and in-person meetings with all partners. Table 5.1 summarizes the meetings held by the project partners:

Table 5.1: HOLOSEU Internal Meetings in Year One.

	Date	Location
Kick-off meeting	January 8 th 2025	Virtual
Kick-off meeting	March 10 th –12 th 2025	Dublin
Communication Plan preparation meeting (M7.2)	February 14 th 2025	Dublin
Steering Committee and HOLOSEU progress meeting	July 2 nd 2025	Virtual
Quarterly meeting	October 17 th 2025	Virtual

5.3 Delivery Channels

"Delivery channels" refer to the methods used to share information with stakeholders. Choosing the preferred channel of your audience is essential, as it is equally important as creating the right message for the right stakeholders at the right time.

Examples of delivery channels:

- Brochures
- Conferences
- Demonstrations
- Email
- Newsletters
- Posters
- Speaking engagements
- Team meetings

- Exhibitions
- Flyers
- Fact sheets
- Website
- Workshops
- project Roll-up

6 Communications and Dissemination Plan

In the following we list the communications activities that are required to keep the right stakeholders informed with the right information, at the right time. In subchapter 6.1 Communications Schedule we show the distribution of activities over time, while in subchapter 6.2 Communications Activities we describe them in more detail.

6.1 Communication schedule

In the following table each of the Communications events that HOLOSEU partners intend to hold to disseminate the communications messages to the stakeholders, is scheduled. The living document for updates is uploaded in our shared drive. Reminders will be sent to the consortium to ask for regular updates.

6.2 Communications Activities

The following table describes the communications activities listed in the schedule above in more depth.

Type	#	Activity title	Start Date	End Date	KPIs
Communication activities	C1	HOLOSEU website holoseu.net	2025-03-01	2027-12-31	A multilingual website open in M2 and launch in M3, for regular updates on research progress, aiming for over 30K visitors
	C2	Meetings with the HOLOSEU consultation board/Steering Committee	2025-03-01	2027-12-31	A Steering Committee will be established at the kick-off meeting, comprising the Project Coordinator, three partners, an ICT-AGRI-FOOD representative, two international scientists, and one stakeholder, to ensure adherence to scientific, technical, and ethical standards.
	C3	Collaborations and Partnerships Management	2025-01-01	2027-12-31	Creation of 15 new collaborations and 5 collaborative projects Collaborations with ReLive, ICT-AGRI-FOOD
	C4	Stakeholder engagement and requirement gathering	2025-03-01	2027-10-31	Regular team meetings, quarterly virtual meetings (P1) 3 stakeholder workshops organized in conjunction with other EU projects to maximize attendance and interest (P9)
	C7	Final HOLOSEU event with final meeting (and release with a version of the HOLOSEU application)	2027-11-01	2027-12-31	1 final event
	C9	Social media posts https://www.linkedin.com/company/holoseu/posts/?feedView=all	2025-03-01	2027-12-31	14 popular articles/ blogs Regular updates, interaction with 500+ stakeholders (minimum) if relevant results can be shared by the workpackages, we opt for posting on a weekly basis from the HOLOSEU accounts
	C10	Blogs	2025-03-01	2027-12-31	7 blogs
	C10	Infographics	2025-07-01	2027-12-31	high-quality, visually compelling materials, including interactive data visualizations, infographic summaries, explanatory videos, digital stories, and interactive dashboards supported by AI tools, simplifying complex scientific data into accessible, engaging formats
	C11	Posters/roll-ups	2025-07-01	2027-12-31	Project poster/brochure/ one-pager
	C15	Webinars	2025-07-01	2027-12-31	Providing project findings and discussions in accessible formats

Table 6.1: Communication Activities for year 2025-2027

Table 6.2: Partners Communication Activity Summary in Year One.

Activity title	Target 2025	UCD (P1)	Avoin (P2)	IPAN (P4)	YOBU (P6)	USAMV (P7)	UNIA (P8)	FH ISI (P9)
HOLOSEU website	1	1						
Meetings with the HOLOSEU consultation board/Steering Committee	1	1						
Collaborations and Partnerships Management	15 collaborations, 5 collaborative projects (in total)							1
Stakeholder engagement and	1		2					1

requirement gathering								
Social media posts	7	73	1	No update	1	18	0	0
Infographics	7 (in total)							
Posters/roll-ups	14 (in total)							
Webinars	3 (in total)							

Table 6.3: Possible Collaborators for HOLOSEU Project.

Project	Contact Partner	Response Status
Digital vegetable field	ISI	Contacted 24/11/2025
DAKIS	ISI	Meeting with project contact person and UCD in May 2025
Small4Good	ISI	Contacted 24/11/2025; response: After short discussion with our research director and department head, we concluded that it seems that our research topics do not match so well. We clearly focus on forestry topics and see only very few matching points between HOLOSEU and our projects.
SNaPwürZ	ISI	Contacted 24/11/2025, answered 24/11/2025, online meeting with UCD on the 9th of December 2025
DairyMix (ICT-AGRI-FOOD)	ISI	Contacted 24/11/2025, answered 24/11/2025, no time this year, asked for a meeting in 2026 on 26/11/2025
Dr. Katja Klumpp (INRAE)	UCD	No updates
HOLOSIE	UCD	No updates
Dr. Tony	YOBU	No answer
EJP SOIL/ CIRCASA/ SPECTORS	YOBU	No answer
EXPRESS	ISI	FH ISI contacted project contact person and there is an interest in cooperation
ICT-AGRI-FOOD Projects	UCD	No updates
LUKE	UCD	Contacted 24/11/2025
Mr. İskender Demirtaş	YOBU	Answered 02/12/2025

6.3 Dissemination Activities

Type	#	Activity title	Start Date	End Date	KPIs
Dissemination activities	DA.1	Scientific presentations in conferences and exhibitions	2025-01-01	2027-12-31	24 conference presentations (e.g., EGU European Geosciences Union (>1000 attendees), Global Research Alliance (500), ICOS (300)), with attendance numbers collected from organizers. Scientific results will be shared through collaborations with ICT-AGRI-FOOD, ERA-NET, GRA, and other relevant groups
	DA.2	Peer-reviewed scientific publications (incl. one article by P8 as part of D6.1, and one by P6+P7 as part of D6.2, in M32)	2025-01-01	2027-12-31	12 journal articles
	D1.1	D1.1 Comprehensive open agricultural dataset	2025-08-01	2025-08-31	deliverable submitted
	D1.2	D1.2 FAIR data repository and integration report	2026-12-01	2026-12-31	deliverable submitted
	D1.3	D1.3 Data validation and calibration report	2026-04-01	2026-04-30	deliverable submitted
	D2.1	D2.1 A common protocol for data analytics and model development	2025-04-01	2025-04-30	deliverable submitted
	D2.2	D2.2 Maps with an integrated database for HOLOSEU	2026-01-01	2026-01-31	deliverable submitted
	D2.3	D2.3 Preliminary projection framework for climate change/extremes	2027-11-01	2027-11-30	deliverable submitted
	D3.1	D3.1 HOLOSEU MUI design ready	2026-12-01	2026-12-31	deliverable submitted
	D3.2	D3.2 Launch of the open-source Sub component Simulation Models	2027-12-01	2027-12-31	deliverable submitted
	D4.1	D4.1 HOLOSEU prototype	2026-04-01	2026-04-30	deliverable submitted
	D4.2	D4.2 Launch of the HOLOSEU v1.0 Platform	2026-12-01	2026-12-31	deliverable submitted
	D4.3	D4.3 HOLOSEU v3.0 release for implementation	2027-11-01	2027-11-30	deliverable submitted
	D5.1	D5.1 A common experimental protocol	2025-04-01	2025-04-30	deliverable submitted
	D5.2	D5.2 List of data including algorithms and EFs	2027-12-01	2027-12-31	deliverable submitted
	D5.3.1	D5.3.1 A progress report and two scientific articles	2027-02-01	2027-02-28	deliverable submitted
	D5.3.2	D5.3.2 A progress report and two scientific articles	2027-11-01	2027-11-30	deliverable submitted
	D6.1.1	D6.1.1 List of biodiversity indicators	2026-02-01	2026-02-28	deliverable submitted
	D6.1.2	D6.1.2 Prototype of agrobiodiversity module	2027-04-01	2027-04-30	deliverable submitted
	D6.2.1	D6.2.1 An ups calable list of bioeconomy indicators	2026-02-01	2026-02-28	deliverable submitted
	D6.2.2	D6.2.2 Prototype of circular bioeconomy module	2027-04-01	2027-04-30	deliverable submitted
	D7.1	D7.1 A Steering Committee and updated project management plan	2025-03-01	2025-03-31	deliverable submitted
	D7.2	D7.2 Strategic communication plan and reports	2025-03-01	2027-12-31	deliverable submitted
	D7.3.1	D7.3.1 Social media and website launch	2025-03-01	2025-03-31	deliverable submitted
D7.3.2	D7.3.2 Workshop reports	2026-07-01	2026-07-31	deliverable submitted	

Table 6.4 Dissemination Activities for year 2025-2027

Deliverables and other dissemination activities by partners for year one are summarized in the table below.

Table 6.4: Partners Dissemination Activity Summary in Year One.

Activity title	Target 2025	UCD (P1)	Avoin (P2)	IPAN (P4)	YOBU (P6)	USAMV (P7)	UNIA (P8)	FH ISI (P9)
Scientific presentations in conferences and exhibitions	8			4		3		1
Peer-reviewed scientific publications	0	6				2		
D1.1 Comprehensive open agricultural dataset	1					1		
D2.1 A common protocol for data analytics and model development	1	No update						
D5.1 A common experimental protocol	1			No update				
D7.1 A Steering Committee and updated project management plan	1	No update						
D7.2 Strategic communication plan and reports	1							1
D7.3.1 Social media and website launch	1	1						

Detailed dissemination activities in year one are listed in table below.

Table 6.5: Dissemination Activities Performed by Partners in Year One: Detailed Information on Posters, Presentations and Publications.

Partner Name	Activity type	Title	Description	Date
UCD	Publication	Reflecting on surface albedo and climate	Climate Research	2025
UCD	Publication	Automating Spatial Data Integration for HOLOS-IE: Irish Case Study with Soil and Land Cover	Environmental and Earth Sciences	2025
UCD	Publication	Stakeholder Perspectives on Current Agri-Environmental Measures and HOLOS-IE Digital Platform Development.	MDPI Agronomy	2025
UCD	Publication	HOLOS-IE: A System Model for Assessing Carbon Emissions and	EGU General Assembly 2025	2025

		Balance in Agricultural Systems.		
UCD	Publication	Reframing Grassland-Livestock Systems for Sustainable Land Transitions: A Digital Modelling Approach Aligned with Climate and Nature-Based Goals.	2nd International Electronic Conference on Land	2025
UCD	Publication	Developing Grassland System Modules for HOLOS-IE Focusing on Carbon Footprint Accounting Driven by Soils, Climate and Management Approaches.	ENVIRON 2025 University College Dublin (UCD)	2025
USAMV	Presentation	CASEE	CASEE, University of Novi Sad	June 24th –26th 2025
USAMV	Presentation	EUFRIN	EUFRIN, Management Committee	August 24th –26th 2025
USAMV	Review Paper	Sustainable approaches to agricultural greenhouse gas mitigation in the EU: practices, mechanisms, and policy integration.	MDPI	2025
USAMV	Review Paper	Synergistic impacts of bioeconomy and circular economy practices on greenhouse gas dynamics in agriculture.	AgroLife Scientific Journal	In publishing
IPAN	Poster	Agricultural emissions and climate impacts. The mitigation strategies according to the HOLOSEU as digital platform for land use planning	VII Eurosoil 2025	September 8 th –12 th 2025
IPAN	Poster	How can agroforestry regulate greenhouse gas exchange in agricultural soils?	VII Eurosoil 2025	September 8 th –12 th 2025
IPAN	Presentation	Multidimensional benefits of agroforestry in the face of climate change	Workshops for young researchers	November 18 th –19 th 2025
IPAN	Poster	Wpływ wybranych praktyk rolniczych na emisję gazów cieplarnianych z gleb w dobie globalnych zmian klimatu na przykładzie badań prowadzonych w ramach projektu HOLOSEU (in Polish)	Congress of Polish Geography	September 10 th –14 th 2025

USAMV	Presentation	HOLOSEU: advancing climate-resilient agriculture through integrated decision-support tools.	Agriculture for Life, Life for Agriculture	June 5 th –7 th 2025
FH ISI	Presentation	Agribusiness scenarios 2035 for valorization of biodiversity and ecosystem services in the agri-food value chain.	ENVIRON 2025	2025

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

To ensure that diverse target groups receive appropriate messages through the most effective channels at the right time, it is essential to plan communication and dissemination activities well in advance. Changes may arise during the project lifecycle, necessitating the implementation of mechanisms to monitor the progress and effectiveness of the communication plan in meeting its objectives.

After the completion of each communications event, feedback is necessary on whether it was successful. An update of the communication plan will occur by month 14, 25 and 36, incorporating guidelines such as regular evaluations of communication activities to identify the most effective methods, prioritizing the quality of stakeholder engagement over quantity for maximum impact. The effectiveness of these activities will be measured by active engagement from the target audience, using HOLOSEU KPIs to track the success of communicating research outcomes.

The metrics to be followed include presenting research results at major conferences and workshops, with attendance numbers collected from organizers. Meetings, seminars, and workshops will be arranged, inviting stakeholders and data generators, and counting their active participation in agricultural and forestry research with a focus on GHG emissions and mitigation. A dedicated webpage will be developed and maintained, providing regular updates on research progress and objectives, aiming for over 30K visitors. All activities will acknowledge ICT-AGRI-FOOD.

7.1 Feedback Measures and Success Criteria

Feedback from the partners will be collected on a regular basis incorporated in the update of the communication plan (M14, M25, M36). The success of the communication activities will be evaluated using the KPIs.

8 Risk Management in Communication

Risk management in communication serves as a crucial framework for identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential risks that may impact the effectiveness of internal and external messaging. It enhances the ability to respond to unforeseen events and adapt communication strategies accordingly, ensuring that stakeholders remain informed and engaged.

- Selection of suitable external expert for Steering Committee formation: Partners having good liaisons with project-relevant experts will be contacted directly to bring them on board.
- Delay in report/article submissions: Feedback process within the consortium to support on-time delivery.
- Limited response of stakeholders: Various communication media (in person and online) will be used to gather stakeholder insights while promoting HOLOSEU.

ANNEX A: Detailed information on the communication activities in 2025

Partner 1

Social Media Post:

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0fx4tu8efXoFGt7Lu3DHYM7X1zR4ozXQu846Dv56nVNxog8QC3GfSL2GhVTqYtGnil&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02zreRc8gdhP2iLNNGDRgR568gz4w1xcrMLo2e4fSda2tALNfCmgZwUJU2GdAk492Cl&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02HhkRbPZHqXGneFj4xzkjfzMJKGTjm34vJ92eUUdEezwc5X6LU1zVP8L4gDRQEpM3l&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0w3pm3ZWWxvAh8cf4d9S6q5qhXf7CNRxDJke4eWFsF8PphTL3vR8zeFdwFrVVP93GI&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0DSptYP11oMhnoRzCjBQTURT2RV7vv4viZRwVcT2SH4vqGB3Ki5nRXTBpmmzEEKx9l&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02J1SZcDpmonaGfcWBibwJ3Kzn3mA4yVJn39EsbvYC68ohSszegnE7jT3xHYRNC4hl&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid036As7hxZmcyhrTdBkGjTfBA56azFUTEbfffHe3ESuyGCYTmbx9UtDjvcehS9DoRI&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0EimA8pbY9TTgPRorhMA7iEy1HyiCUio43cG2Q8jqBc2UyeuLimQtKGaV2WEq6XHUI&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02oZVcj6PYZshLVpeCZoJpkniPreGyZwFPCU8pzw8wLJC7MsmkRZYLoMY2XTw765BSl&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02Ru98wbvEcB6cAbZnXbzVpuMgDQxhB56TkNyWHT3JQ35iAu4B69TdCX4Nq3g7yJ9kl&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02SEUHHUWLvo8fqXAaHkcnnMgkQfB7YS1N6xMPHwbM6wC24CW2YuJhRr3fwwu5LqV2l&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid021fiVdUEZRAEDScMEq8FUyDbEDHKu8LLJUm9j6hMncDLapRWcrEaTzchBeeSP9cBql&id=100091396220439, Public; Meta

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Partner 2

C4: Stakeholder engagement and requirement gathering:

Presenting the project 1st time to Finnish policymakers, academics, farm advisory organisations, NGOs, and 2 peer projects from the same call, 17.06.2025, Teams

Presenting the project 2nd time to Finnish policymakers, academics, farm advisory organisations, NGOs, and 2 peer projects from the same call, 03.12.2025, Teams

Partner 6

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Partner 7

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Project roll-up

Project webpage:

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